

CyVerse Discovery Environment: A Technological Solution to the Reproducibility Crisis in Scientific Research

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Abstract—This paper examines the potential of the CyVerse Discovery Environment (DE) to address the reproducibility crisis in research. The DE is a platform designed to facilitate data-driven discoveries through reproducible analyses. Reproducibility is ensured by maintaining records of the software, its dependencies, and instructions for its execution. The DE also provides a RESTful web interface, the Terrain API, for creating custom user interfaces. The application of the DE is illustrated through a use case involving the University of Arizona Superfund Research Center, where the DE’s data storage capabilities were utilized to manage data and processes. The paper concludes that the DE facilitates efficient and reproducible research, eliminating the need for substantial hardware investment and complex data management, thereby propelling scientific progress.

Index Terms—containerization technology, CyVerse Discovery Environment (DE), reproducibility crisis, research reproducibility, transparent research, computational environments

I. INTRODUCTION

For years, research reproducibility has gained increasing attention due to the growing concern over the reliability and validity of scientific findings. There may be some merit for concern: studies have shown that researchers are facing pivotal challenges in reproducing published results [1]. Considering the ongoing reproducibility crisis, it is crucial to explore potential technological solutions that can help overcome this challenge. In this context, containerization plays a critical role in facilitating transparent research and in the sharing and reuse of analytical tools. By enabling researchers to create and share versioned computational environments with the dependencies necessary for a given analysis, containerization can help ensure research workflows are reproducible.

CyVerse Discovery Environment (DE) is a flexible platform service built to foster data-driven discoveries through reproducible analyses. It is designed for researchers who require access to computational analysis tools. Users who are familiar

with a tool’s management can install that tool once into a containerized environment, with all its required dependencies, and make it available to other users of the DE. The tools can be reused by others, removing the need for researchers to invest time, hardware, and software resources for complex installations and the management of intricate dependency trees.

II. DESIGN

The DE has three primary features: data management, app integration, and app execution.

Data management involves managing files within the CyVerse Data Store, which is a petabyte scale data repository hosted on CyVerse hardware. The DE provides a graphical interface for data management tasks throughout the data lifecycle, including the ability for users to share their data with the public, or only with specific DE users, which can help to ease the burden of organizing large data sets.

App integration refers to the process of making computational analysis software available for use within the DE. Users may bring to the DE any piece of software that runs on Linux and conforms to CyVerse’s policies. Once an app has been integrated in the DE, the app integrator is free to share it with selected DE users or publish the app for use by all DE users.

App execution refers to the process of using apps that have been integrated into the DE to analyze data. Depending on the app, a user either runs the app to interactively analyze data or simply waits for the analysis to complete and for the results to be uploaded to the Data Store, CyVerse’s data storage and management service.

The DE makes use of several different pieces of open-source software to perform its tasks. Group management is handled by InCommon’s Grouper group management system. Interactive apps (that is, apps that allow users to explore their data interactively) run within our Kubernetes cluster, with access to

the running app managed by a combination of HAProxy and the NGINX Ingress Controller. Non-interactive apps (that is, apps that analyze the data in the background and upload the results to the Data Store) run in our HTCondor cluster, at the Texas Advanced Computing Center using their TAPIS API, or in the Open Science Grid's HTCondor cluster. Authentication is managed by Keycloak. The CyVerse Data store uses iRODS to manage data storage and sharing. The DE's search index is stored in an Elasticsearch cluster. Finally, the DE stores most of the stateful information required to perform its tasks in a set of PostgreSQL databases.

The DE consists of a suite of microservices deployed within a Kubernetes cluster, with each microservice managing a single aspect of the system. For example, the apps microservice handles all facets of app management in the DE, including integration, sharing, and launching. The data-info microservice acts as an interface to the data store. The various microservices are aggregated in Terrain, which handles authentication and forwards requests to lower-level microservices. The DE is open source, and you can find all of the source code in its dedicated GitHub organization. The DE user interface is written in JavaScript using NEXT.js and React. The back-end microservices are written in a combination of Clojure and Go, with some newer microservices written in Rust. Software container images for both the DE microservices and public apps are stored in CyVerse's Harbor instance. Private apps can be stored in any publicly available container registry.

Reproducibility in the DE is achieved by keeping track of the software, its dependencies, and instructions for running the software. The first step in the process of integrating an app into the DE is to create a container image with the software and all of its dependencies installed. Once the container image has been built, it is uploaded to any publicly available container registry. The next step is to create the tool definition in the DE. In DE parlance, a tool is simply a way to keep track of the information needed to launch a piece of software in a container. This includes a reference to the container registry and tag and the path to the executable file within the container. Next, the user defines the app itself. In the DE, the app refers to the set of instructions that the DE uses to generate the command to run the software. This may include command-line options and positional arguments. The app also includes the information needed for the DE to produce the graphical interface that users see when they launch the app, which can include user input validation or restrictions. Apps can also have multiple versions so that a software update doesn't necessarily have to render analyses performed using previous software versions unreproducible. Finally, when an app is launched, the DE records the parameters that were used, including the Data Store locations for any input data selected for the analysis, enabling users to relaunch the same app version with the same set of parameters, making it as likely as possible that the analysis can be reproduced successfully. These DE analyses may also be shared with other users, which shares the app and any input data (if they are not already public), allowing other DE users to relaunch these analyses

using the same set of parameters and input data, making it easy for them to also reproduce the results. Users also have the opportunity to modify parameters and inputs before relaunching an analysis, or to launch multiple analyses over a set of inputs.

For users with more specialized needs, the DE's Terrain API makes it possible to create custom user interfaces that are capable of utilizing the DE's capabilities. Terrain is a RESTful web interface with an OpenAPI specification for documentation.

III. USE CASE

The University of Arizona Superfund Research Center is a collaboration of over 40 researchers managing five projects funded by the National Institutes of Health (NIH). Their research focuses on the link between arsenic in mine tailings, the environment and diabetes. Their Data Management and Analysis Core (DMAC) integrates the CyVerse into their pipeline within their Demeter App. Demeter is a user interface for a data processing application that automates the processing of related groups of FASTQ files using command line tools. Its purpose is to save money and researcher's time by handling repetitive tasks and to accelerate the discovery process. By leveraging data management, app integration, and app execution, users can benefit from single sign-on, enabling them to access their data and analysis workflows in a central location. The containerized application used to run the data processing has been shared with others in CyVerse, and its versions are documented to ensure reproducibility and allow for analysis using specific versions [2].

IV. CONCLUSION

Using CyVerse for scientific analysis offers benefits over standalone container management due to its comprehensive ecosystem. The DE provides a straightforward interface that researchers can use to both manage and analyze their datasets, large or small. Using the DE allows researchers to spend virtually nothing on hardware, and less time managing their data and dealing with the vagaries of computational analysis software and its often large and complex dependency trees. The DE makes doing science more efficient and reproducible, enabling the research that drives science and knowledge forward.

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